

Research Article

Emerging Trends in Cybersecurity: Issues in Cybersecurity During Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract: *The world is currently facing the COVID-19 pandemic, which is one of the most devastating global health crises of this century. It has affected approximately 10.7 million people worldwide and has caused significant disruption. One notable consequence is the rapid increase in remote work. Organizations also need to adapt to the new reality. However, this shift has exposed a critical concern that employees who work from home often have limited cybersecurity resources compared to organizations with dedicated security teams. This creates vulnerabilities, leaving employees far more vulnerable to potential cyber-attacks. Organizations need to prioritize the security of their dispersed workforce and implement robust cybersecurity measures to protect against these threats. Cybersecurity attacks have become a serious problem. The common types of cyber security attacks are Denial of Service (DoS) and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, Man in the Middle (MitM), Phishing and Spear Phishing attacks, and Malware. Attackers have a clear motive when they target victims with obtaining their credentials or financial rewards. People who engage in online activities are exposed to numerous cyber dangers. This vulnerability arises from the network's inherent insecurity. Attackers possess the skills to exploit the flaws in the Internet's infrastructure, utilizing their coding expertise to their advantage. This research paper focuses more on discussions related to cybersecurity issues during the Covid-19 Pandemic.*

Keywords: *Cyber security, Covid-19, Cyberattack, Cyber threats*

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1. INTRODUCTION

The geography of the globe was promptly altered by the Internet, which first appeared as a platform for communication and exchange. Particularly, the 21st century has been and still is the century in which global geography and the Internet network are interconnected. As a result, the Internet allows for rapid global communication between people, and crucial commercial, political, economic, and cultural ties have been established between states. Computers, users, and networks are the three essential components of the Internet. It has been noted that network technologies have advanced because of the continually evolving computer industry and user segments that have begun to hold a variety of skills. However, the advancement and widespread application of network technologies has also resulted in serious problems with security. To secure the assets of institutions, organizations, and people, efforts have been undertaken to create a cyber security environment.

Networks with infrastructure information systems are referred to as "virtual reality" and are referred to as "cyber" in this context. Communication, life, integration, tangible and intangible assets, and data are all protected by cyber security measures in an electronic setting created by institutions, organizations, and people in information systems. In summary, cyber security guarantees the safety of digital existence on digital networks. Under the general heading of cyber security, the fundamentals of information systems' data integrity and confidentiality are protected. Securing personal and organizational data on the Internet is the main goal of cyber security. Ignorance of this crucial issue may pose major risks. (Omar, Semih, Merve, et al; 2023). Data theft, network, and computer interruptions, and other effects are caused by the attack. Attacks have also increased because of several other issues, such as the improper use of unmanned aerial vehicles. Attacks can be launched using techniques including phishing, ransomware, Denial-of-Services (DoS), and malicious software. An attacker's particular skills and the quantity of information they have about their victim both affect how successful their attack will be. (Mah Hui, Alya, Carin, et al; 2020).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Cybersecurity

Cybersecurity, also known as information technology security or electronic information security, is all about protecting computers, servers, mobile devices, electronic systems, networks, and data from malicious attacks. Its ultimate goal is to safeguard these crucial components from unauthorized access, data breaches, and a wide range of cyber threats. To ensure the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of digital assets, cybersecurity relies on the implementation of preventive measures like robust security protocols, encryption, firewalls, and intrusion detection systems. (Kaspersky, 2023).

In today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, cybersecurity plays an important role in protecting the security, integrity, and confidentiality of various elements in the electronic environment. It serves as an important defense mechanism that protects communication, life, integration, tangible or intangible assets, and data in information systems. Institutions, organizations, and individuals rely on cyber security to create a robust and secure framework that effectively mitigates the risks posed by cyber threats. By implementing comprehensive cyber security measures, they ensure the smooth functioning and protection of their digital infrastructure. Protecting these critical components is essential to fostering trust, preserving privacy, and promoting the overall well-being of individuals and organizations in our interconnected world (Omar, Semih, Merve, et al; 2023).

Another definition of Cybersecurity is Cybersecurity is the protection of internet-connected systems such as hardware, software, and data from cyber threats. The practice is used by individuals and enterprises to protect against unauthorized access to data centers and other computerized systems (Sharon Shea, Alexander; Casey Clark, 2022).

2.2 Cyber Threats

In the digital world, cyber threats or also known as cyber security threats are malicious actions that aim to steal or damage data or disrupt the digital well-being and stability of an enterprise. Cyber threats include a wide variety of attacks from data breaches, to computer viruses, denial of service, and many other attack vectors (Raj Joy, 2023).

Another definition of cyber threat is that it refers to anything that has the potential to cause serious harm to a computer system. Also, a Cyber threat may or may not happen, but can potentially cause serious damage (Margaret Rouse, 2022).

2.3 Denial of Services (DoS)

A Denial-of-Service (DoS) assault could be a cyberattack that disturbs arrange frameworks with untrue demands for the reason of disturbing trade operations. The creator states that as a result of the assault, clients are incapable to perform scheduled assignments, such as getting to e-mail, websites, online accounts, or other assets worked by the influenced computer or arrange (Bart Lenaerts, 2023). In addition, this type of attack bombards target systems to intercept customer service requests, and it happened during the pandemic to slow down response to coronavirus cases. It can be launched from multiple malware-infected servers allowing attackers to take control of them (Khalid Hussain, Syed Jawad Hussain, et al., 2019).

2.4 Man in Middle (MitM)

A Man in The Middle (MITM) assault may be a general term when the culprit places himself within the discussion between the client and the application. The point of the assault is to take individual data, such as login accreditations, account points of interest, and credit card numbers. The target is as a rule clients of monetary applications, e-commerce locales, and other websites that require a login (Erez Hason, 2023). Next, this type of attack happens to be a threat to those who are working from home especially those without security guidance from their companies.

2.5 Phishing and Spear Phishing

Phishing is sending malicious emails designed to trick people into falling for a scam. Typically, the intent is to trick users into disclosing financial information, system credentials, or other sensitive data (Proofpoint, 2020). In addition, another definition of Phishing attack is phishing is a type of cybercrime where the targets are lured or tricked into giving up sensitive information, such as their Social Security Number and personally identifiable information and passwords (Alyssa Anne, Syukrina, Azween, et al., 2019). Phishing assaults imitate emails or social media joins from genuine sources in arrange to get individual data from a target. This sort of assault includes the naivety of human interest and specialized guile. Shapes of conveyance of phishing assaults are through emails that contain malware or join to ill-conceived websites or downloads.

Spear phishing is a type of targeted phishing attack that involves identifying the target and generating personalized messages tailored to the target. This makes education scams difficult to identify, combat, and prevent. Spear phishing can be done with cloned websites to get social media credentials or spoof emails by spoofing the source of the email (Alyssa Anne, Syukrina, Azween, et al., 2019).

2.6 Malicious Software (Malware)

Next is Malware. The short name for Malware is malicious software. Malware is an umbrella term for viruses, worms, trojans, and other malicious computer programs that hackers use to destroy and gain access to sensitive information (Josh Fruhlinger, 2019).

Malware is any undesirable computer program introduced onto a target gadget without the user's consent. Malware can utilize the gadget to spread to other gadgets by reproducing itself and covering up invaluable applications. There are numerous shapes of malware assaults counting, including large-scale infections, record infectors, ransomware, trojans, rationale bombs, etc (Jeff Melnick, 2023).

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Issues and Challenges

Cybercriminals are always developing their methods to accomplish their objectives as technology does. Human causes are the main cause of cyberattacks. Individuals share knowledge online and with other individuals and organizations, making the most of their time to be as productive as possible. During the COVID-19 pandemic, people are susceptible to cyber security due to there is an increase in online activities including e-learning, working from home, online shopping, and others. It might be challenging for everyone to stay updated on new information regarding devices and internet safety in this highly technological digital environment. Additionally, users must make sure that all their devices, including PCs, iPads, and mobile phones, are up to date. However, most individuals prefer to ignore the message asking them to upgrade their device because they believe the updating process will be difficult and take up a lot of memory. The ease with which hackers can access their gadgets makes them vulnerable to cyber security (Home Instead, 2021).

Additionally, other issues in cyber security are there are many security bugs in software applications. During the COVID-19 pandemic, people are likely to download more software applications such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Google Meetings. This is because hackers can create code based on weaknesses in software applications. Devices can be easily attacked if software applications have many unknown security features and bugs. Hackers wrap your code in malware and install it on your device. This makes their respective devices vulnerable and puts them at risk by using malware to attack software vulnerabilities. The device can then be compromised, and hackers gain unauthorized control of the device. They can access anything and steal the victim's information (Norton, 2019).

Another is cloud computing services ended up vulnerable to cybersecurity. It is because people depend on technology as well. The modern tech trend in computer systems is cloud computing. More companies than ever resort to this effective computing system and the amount of data facilitated on these cloud services is amazing. (Chandana, 2022). These days, users store their records on cloud services. Be that as it may, cyberattacks on cloud services have multiplied in 2019, making cloud services the third most focused on stage by cybercriminals right now. Users just not store records on cloud services but also passwords on their browsers for convenience. This facilitates users amid logins by auto-filling the accreditations after the user's confirmation. For case, Google Chrome allows users to save their passwords in his/her Google account. Upon successful login, all the passwords can be read. Thus, if the user's Google account is gotten by an unauthorized user, the unauthorized user will have to get to all his/her other accounts. Having a weak password and utilizing the same password over stages and applications are moreover exceptionally unsafe. Weak passwords can be effectively hacked in minutes. Typically, too why websites have made it compulsory for users to have a strong password that incorporates alphanumeric, special characters, and capitalization. These systems are a few of the juicier targets for modern-day hackers, as indeed a little breach of security can demonstrate sadly. To avoid any issues, businesses utilizing this system must continually discuss and request the finest security systems from their cloud service suppliers (Mah Hui, Alya, Carin, et al; 2020).

In addition, misleading data moreover makes people vulnerable to cyber security during the COVID-19 widespread. Attackers will attempt to trap an individual into giving them a few important data or their accreditations such as username, password, and credit card number so that the attacker can enter the victim's device and download malware in their device. The most common sort of phishing attack uses mail as its essential tool. Victims will get fake emails and on the off chance that they press on malicious joins, ransomware or malware can be installed in their devices. Phishing attacks are usually utilized to target individuals or organizations so that attackers can take advantage of them. This

strategy will cause theft of individual information such as personality card numbers, addresses, account bank data, and so on.

3.2 Types of Cybersecurity Threats

One of the foremost common types of cyber-attacks is phishing and spear phishing attacks. Phishing attacks imitate emails or social media links from legitimate sources to get individual data from a target. This type of attack includes the naivety of human interest and technical deceit. Forms of conveyance of phishing attacks are through emails that contain malware or join to ill-conceived websites or downloads. Spear phishing could be a focused-on type of phishing attack, which includes surveillance of the target and making personalized messages that are significant to the target. This makes spear phishing troublesome to identify, protect and avoid. Spear phishing can be done with website cloning to get social media logins or mail spoofing by forging the root of the mail or sender's mail address. For example, we found phishing attacks generally centered around Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and testing kits in March 2020, government jolt programs from April through the summer of 2020 counting a fake U.S. Exchanging Commission website that postured as the U.S. Of note, that from December 2020 to February 2021, vaccine-related phishing attempts increased by 530%, while those targeting pharmacies and hospitals increased by 189% during the same period. (Lucas Hu, 2021).

Another type of cybersecurity threat is Denial of Service (DoS) and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks. This type of attack is a target system to block service demands from clients, and it has happened during the pandemic to slow down response to coronavirus cases. It can be propelled from numerous machines that have been infected with malware that allows the attacker control over them. DoS attacks do not deliver the attacker a direct advantage unless the attack was propelled by a competitor or propelled to execute another type of attack. There are numerous ways to execute a DoS attack, such as an SYN flood attack, tear attack, smurf attack, ping of death assault, and botnets. For case, the cybersecurity attack scene in 2020 was caused by the COVID-19 widespread. The report states that DDoS attacks proceed to be the biggest disturbance during the COVID-19 pandemic and within the predictable future. Also, the high volume of online shopping occasioned by the COVID-19 widespread led to expanded DDoS attacks during the Movement Control Order (MCO). (Alicia Hope, 2021).

4. DISCUSSION

Among the cyber security issues listed in the findings section are Phishing and Spear Phishing attacks and the next issue is A Denial-of-Service (DoS). But Phishing attacks are more and are the main issue that will be discussed. Phishing occurs when fraudsters try to obtain sensitive information or data from you by portraying themselves as a reliable source. Phishers use a variety of places to carry out their cyberattacks, including email, SMS, and phone calls. According to Security Magazine (2022), in the magazine's writing titled "More than 255m phishing attacks in 2022 so far". In the magazine, the authors stated that 23.6% was the rate of total phishing attacks recorded in the first quarter of 2022. The financial industry was the most targeted industry at that time. Furthermore, the magazine also stated that as many as 255 million phishing cases were recorded throughout the six months of 2022 (Nivedita James, 2023). In addition, there is a study conducted by the AICPA in 2018 stating that it is reported that almost 60% of Americans have been victims of fraud schemes and 26% have been exposed to email phishing scams (Clare Stouffer, 2022). According to a report made by Verizon, 2022 phishing is one of the main causes of data breaches which is often a major problem (Verizon, 2022). According to a report issued by the FBI, 2020 states that they received the highest number of internet crime phishing reports in 2020, with a total of 241,342 victims (Clare Stouffers, 2022).

In 2019, which is the middle of December 2019, the world was shocked by the news of the emergence of a new virus. The Covid-19 virus is the name given to this virus. According to sources from the World Health Organization (WHO), this virus started in the city of Wuhan, Hubei, China. So,

the World Health Organization has decided to recognize that Covid-19 started on March 11, 2020 (WHO, 2020). Since Covid-19 is spreading all over the world and this also indirectly causes cases to increase from time to time. Governments all across the world have taken various measures to halt the spread of the virus. The example of Malaysia, which is no exception in facing this crisis, has taken steps by implementing the Movement Control Order (MCO). According to a source from Berita Harian, Tan Sri Muhyiddin Yassin, who was the Prime Minister at the time, had implemented the order to curb the spread of this epidemic from continuing to spread among Malaysians. The Prime Minister issued a Movement Control Order from March 18 to March 31, 2020. This Movement Control Order applies to the entire state and no one is exempt (Berita Harian, 2021).

After the emergence of the epidemic, we can witness the emergence of many cases of fraud, cases of phishing attacks involving individuals, organizations, or businesses. Next, according to the author, a study conducted by the NCSC (National Cyber Security Center), it was stated that they had received 350 cases of attacks involving phishing, online fraud, and more (Swissinfo, 2020). This case occurred in Switzerland in April 2020. The NCSC also compared the number before Covid-19 existed, which is on a normal day when only 100 to 150 cases were reported. As a result, Covid-19 has been labeled as the main factor in the increase in the number of cases in Switzerland (Cedric Nabe, 2022). This situation occurs because the work pattern during the Covid-19 pandemic has changed significantly where the government has ordered workers to work from home only and a person's movement is limited due to restrictions that have been ordered by the government (Cedric Nabe, 2022). Working remotely has a very low level of internet security and it's not like in the workplace which definitely has a high level of cyber security. Evidence can be seen through a study obtained by Swissinfo, 2020 in which it recorded as many as 47% of individuals who have been involved in phishing fraud syndicates while working at home. Phishers take the opportunity to further expand their reach by exploiting the weaknesses of workers who work from home. For example spreading fake news related to Coronavirus (Cedric Nabe, 2022).

5. CONCLUSION

To conclude the research, it is observed that cybersecurity is a field of study that should not be disregarded as we are moving towards an age of digital technology, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Blockchain, the Internet of Things (IoT), and the like. Nonetheless, some cybercriminals are more frequent and sophisticated. Cybercriminals are instilling fear into the population, becoming more assertive and fearless as cybersecurity is not enforced, maintained, and enhanced. E-mail phishing threats (Alawida, Omolara, Abiodun, and Al-Rajab, 2022) and vulnerability to cybersecurity threats (Chgada and Madzinga, 2021) are the most common example of cybersecurity attacks that occur every day and night during the COVID-19 pandemic. It is probably due to hackers being so busy launching different variants of cybersecurity attacks that can harm economic transactions and computer-based systems.

Even though many business owners, companies, and organizations have turned to digital security to ensure the longevity of their business, it is believed that many businesses ignore the threats of cybersecurity attacks, or cyberattacks during the COVID-19 pandemic and the total lockdown. Cyberattacks can be dynamic and affect all computer-based systems and the Internet environment by manipulating the attack format and target audience. The increase in cyberattacks is usually caused by different factors such as technical and non-technical reasons, the transfer of social life to the Internet environment, errors and vulnerabilities in software, and so on.

To efficiently and effectively protect computer-based systems from cyberattacks, extensive protection is required, such as technical solutions that significantly improve the ability to scan for data breaches, find vulnerabilities in computer systems and communication networks, and enhance the

accuracy of attack detection systems, Although, there are still some issues and challenges to effectively detecting new and complex cyber-attacks. Meanwhile, overcoming the issues and challenges of cybersecurity attacks is especially important to enhance people's security in the future. Also, when experiencing the attacks firsthand, most business owners should take action on countering cybersecurity attacks, by owning a security policy, purchasing equipment or software required to maintain the security, hiring security professionals such as ethical hackers to perform penetration testing, and allowing administrators to modify sensitive information.

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References

- Ahmad Kamal, A.H.; Yi Yen, C.C.; Ping, M.H.; Zahra, F. Cybersecurity Issues and Challenges during Covid-19 Pandemic. *Preprints.org* 2020, 2020090249. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202009.0249.v1>
- Eian, I.C.; Yong, L.K.; Li, M..Y.X.; Qi, Y.H.; Z, F. Cyber Attacks in the Era of COVID-19 and Possible Solution Domains. *Preprints.org* 2020, 2020090630. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202009.0630.v1>
- Aslan, Ö.; Aktu ğ, S.S.; Ozkan-Okay, M.; Yilmaz, A.A.; Akin, E. A Comprehensive Review of Cyber Security Vulnerabilities, Threats, Attacks, and Solutions. *Electronics* 2023, 12, 1333. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12061333>
- Ubing, A. A., Jasmi, S. Z. A., Abdullah, A., Zaman, N., & Supramaniam, M. (2019). Phishing Website Detection: An Improved Accuracy through Feature Selection and Ensemble Learning. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.14569/ijacsa.2019.0100133>
- Hu, L. (2021, March 24). Fake Websites Used in COVID-19-Themed Phishing Attacks, Impersonating Brands Like Pfizer and BioNTech. *Unit 42*. [https://unit42.paloaltonetworks.com/covid-19-themed-phishing-attacks/#:~:text=We%20found%20phishing%20attacks%20largely,to%20steal%20user%20credentials\)%20and](https://unit42.paloaltonetworks.com/covid-19-themed-phishing-attacks/#:~:text=We%20found%20phishing%20attacks%20largely,to%20steal%20user%20credentials)%20and)
- Hope, A. (2021, January 29). DDoS Attacks Increased Rapidly During the COVID-19 Pandemic as Hackers Exploited New Tools and Techniques. *CPO Magazine*. <https://www.cpomagazine.com/cyber-security/ddos-attacks-increased-rapidly-during-the-covid-19-pandemic-as-hackers-exploited-new-tools-and-techniques/>
- Chandana. (2022). Cyber Security Risks in the todays Era of Digitalization. *Simplilearn.com*. https://www.simplilearn.com/cyber-security-8-vulnerable-risks-article#2_cloud_computing_services
- James, N. (2023, April 3). *Phishing attack statistics 2023: The ultimate insight*. Astra Security Blog. https://www.getastra.com/blog/security-audit/phishing-attack-statistics/?utm_feeditemid=&utm_device=c&utm_term=&utm_source=google&utm_medium=cpc&utm_campaign=Dynamic%2Bads%2B-%2BCampaign%2B-%2BPentest&hsa_cam=17272935963&hsa_grp=153763431830&hsa_mt=&hsa_src=g&hsa_ad=660848984559&hsa_acc=8352936176&hsa_net=adwords&hsa_kw=&hsa_tgt=dsa-2082491362765&hsa_ver=3&gclid=CjwKCAjwsvujBhAXEiwA UXnADzU9ak7Dm7uiv1WLJM809ZD11u7NTDljNo9dc2N4HwiYJQMTLdQmxcCZN8QAvD BwE
- Cost of a data breach 2022*. IBM. (n.d.). <https://www.ibm.com/reports/data-breach>
- Cassetto, O. (2023, May 1). *Cybersecurity threats: Types and challenges*. Exabeam. <https://www.exabeam.com/information-security/cyber-security-threat/>
- Shea, S., Gillis, A. S., & Clark, C. (2023, January 11). *What is cybersecurity? everything you need to know: TechTarget*. Security. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchsecurity/definition/cybersecurity>

Tessian. (2023, April 12). *Why we click on phishing scams - how to avoid being hacked*. Tessian. <https://www.tessian.com/blog/why-we-click-on-phishing-scams/#:~:text=In%20a%20recent%20survey%20conducted,a%20phishing%20email%20at%20work>

Roy, R., 23, L. U. A., Raj Roy opens a new window opens a new window Raj leads the editorial sponsorship, Raj Roy opens a new window, & opens a new window Raj leads the editorial sponsorship and premium content program at ToolBox. With over 8 years of experience in 360 digital marketing. (2021, August 23). *What is a cyber threat? What Definition, types, hunting, best practices, and examples?* Spiceworks. https://www.spiceworks.com/it-security/vulnerability-management/articles/what-is-cyber-threat/#_001

Margaret Rouse Margaret Rouse is an award-winning technical writer and teacher known for her ability to explain complex technical subjects simply to a non-technical, Rouse, M., Margaret Rouse is an award-winning technical writer and teacher known for her ability to explain complex technical subjects simply to a non-technical, Editor, April, L. updated: 25, & updated: L. (2022, April 25). *Cyberthreat*. Techopedia. <https://www.techopedia.com/definition/25263/cyberthreat>

What is a denial of service (dos) attack? - crowd strike. crowdstrike.com. (2023, April 21). <https://www.crowdstrike.com/cybersecurity-101/denial-of-service-dos-attacks/>

What is phishing? - definition, types of attacks & more: Proofpoint us. Proofpoint. (2023, May 29). <https://www.proofpoint.com/us/threat-reference/phishing>

Fruhlinger, J. (2019, May 17). *What is malware: Definition, examples, detection, and recovery*. CSO Online. <https://www.csoonline.com/article/3295877/what-is-malware-viruses-worms-trojans-and-beyond.html>

Alawida, M., Omolara, A.E., Abiodun, O.I., Al-Rajab, M. (2022). *A deeper look into cybersecurity issues in the wake of Covid-19: A survey*. *Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences*. Vol. 34 (10), pp 8176–206. doi: 10.1016/j.jksuci.2022.08.003. Epub 2022 Aug 11. PMID: PMC9367180.

Chigada, J. & Madzinga, R. (2021). *Cyberattacks and threats during COVID-19: A systematic literature review*. *SA Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 23 (1). 10.4102/sajim.v23i1.1277.

Zerlang, J. (2022, July 20). *The Pandemic's Lasting Effects: Are Cyber Attacks One of Them?* Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbestechcouncil/2022/07/20/the-pandemics-lasting-effects-are-cyber-attacks-one-of-them/?sh=9def68f2b76c>

Lohrmann, D. (2022, August 21). *Hacktivism and DDOS attacks rise dramatically in 2022*. GovTech. <https://www.govtech.com/blogs/lohmann-on-cybersecurity/hacktivism-and-ddos-attacks-rise-dramatically-in-2022>

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279 8090 . (2020, December 15). *Impact of covid-19 on Cybersecurity*. Deloitte Switzerland. <https://www2.deloitte.com/ch/en/pages/risk/articles/impact-covid-cybersecurity.html>

Kronologi Pelaksanaan FASA PKP | Nasional | Berita Harian - BH Online. (n.d.). <https://api.bharian.com.my/berita/nasional/2021/01/775155/kronologi-pelaksanaan-fasa-pkp>